

The Potential Impact of Large Language Models on Doctor-Patient Communication: A Case Study in Prostate Cancer

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Abstract: (1) **Background:** In 1949, Claude Shannon and Warren Weaver introduced the linear model of communication, later adopted across various fields, including health. The integration of large language models (LLMs) into healthcare presents both challenges and opportunities for the doctor-patient relationship, having the potential to introduce both facilitative and disruptive elements to the linear model of doctor-patient communication. (2) **Methods:** The objective of the study was to evaluate critically the performance of three large language models widely available - ChatGPT, Co-Pilot, and Gemini—compared to the Patient's Guide on prostate cancer in a well-defined cultural environment and to inform the development of a personalized the doctor-patient communication model. (3) **Results:** The results offer useful insights into the assessment of different LLMs by a group of experts based on various criteria. The ANOVA analysis revealed significant main effects for both tools and criteria and a significant interaction between tools and criteria. This suggests that the performance of the tools varied depending on the assessment criterion. The results demonstrate that while individual experts varied in scoring tendencies, the overall evaluations were consistent and reliable when considered as a group. The findings also highlight that the performance of different LLMs varies significantly across evaluation criteria, emphasizing the importance of a multidimensional assessment approach when comparing such tools. (4) **Conclusions:** In the context of prostate cancer, where precise and empathetic communication is critical, LLMs can potentially play a transformative role. Our results bring forth several implications for the contemporary design of the doctor-patient relationship and the transition towards a truly personalized health communication model: the right message from the right doctor at the right time for the right patient.

Keywords: prostate cancer, ChatGPT, Co-Pilot, Gemini, cancer literacy, large language models, doctor-patient relationship

1. Introduction

The doctor-patient relationship is a cornerstone of medical practice, tracing its roots back to ancient civilizations like Egypt and Greece, where healers were viewed with a mix of mystical reverence and trust [1]. Hippocrates, often considered the father of modern medicine, formalized this relationship through his ethical principles, emphasizing confidentiality and patient welfare [2]. As medicine progressed through the Middle Ages and into the Renaissance [3], the dynamics of the relationship shifted with increased emphasis on scientific understanding, yet the fundamental elements of empathy and confidentiality remained central. [4]

The 20th century introduced more complexities with technological advancements and greater patient autonomy, leading to today's model. During the industrial revolutions, the doctor-patient relationship underwent significant transformations in response to the profound societal changes brought about by industrialization. [5] The 4th Industrial Revolution, characterized by the integration of digital, biological, and physical technologies [6], has further evolved the doctor-patient relationship. Innovations such as telemedicine, electronic health records (EHRs), and AI-driven health technologies have transformed how doctors and patients interact [7]. This era also marked the beginning of professional medical associations and the standardization of medical training and practices, which professionalized the field and altered the dynamic between doctors and patients. This catalyzed a shift from more personal and individualized doctor-patient interaction to a more systematic and formalized approach in medical practice, laying the groundwork for modern medical bureaucracy and clinical practices.

In 1949, Claude Shannon and Warren Weaver introduced the linear model of communication, often referred to as the Shannon-Weaver model [8]. This foundational concept was originally developed to enhance telephone communication and later adopted across various fields, including health [9].

After the public launch of ChatGPT in November 2022, Large Language Models (LLMs) began to be used for various purposes in the healthcare field, from patient information and medical education to simplifying bureaucratic processes in medical institutions and improving the diagnosis and treatment of various diseases. [10-12]

The integration of large language models (LLMs) into healthcare presents both challenges and opportunities for the doctor-patient relationship, having the potential to introduce both facilitative and disruptive elements to the linear model of doctor-patient communication. [13-16]

The objective of our study was to critically evaluate the performance of three widely available large language models—ChatGPT, Gemini, and Co-Pilot—compared to the Patient's Guide on prostate cancer [17] within a well-defined cultural environment. Based on the findings, we aim to contribute to the development of a new conceptual model for doctor-patient communication in the era of LLMs concerning prostate cancer.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study design

The study's approach was devised to systematically evaluate the effectiveness of three prominent language models (LLMs: Co-Pilot, ChatGPT, Gemini) in comparison to the official Romanian Patient's Guide on prostate cancer (i.e., the Guide). The evaluation focused on the models' ability to deliver precise, timely, understandable, and user-friendly information on prostate cancer. We dubbed these four criteria under the following labels: *accuracy*, *timeliness*, *comprehensiveness*, and being *friendly*. Consequently, we produced a set of 25 inquiries that encompass frequently asked issues concerning prostate cancer. For replication purposes, the code and the data are freely available [18]. The subsequent prompt was employed to query the three LLMs: *I am a man, and my doctor has informed me that I have been diagnosed with prostate cancer. I am interested in learning more about the diagnosis, treatment, and overall management of the disease, which will help me better manage the condition and improve my quality of life. Therefore, I have the following questions for which I would like to obtain answers.* One operator performed queries on all three models to maintain uniformity in the process of collecting data. The questions were performed in incognito mode on Google Chrome to prevent any customized search biases, guaranteeing that each LLM answered simply based on their own expertise and algorithms. Upon gathering the responses, we used a randomized procedure to fully blend the answers. The purpose of this process was to guarantee that the future examination by experts would be devoid of any prior biases regarding the origin of each response.

2.2 Participants and Setting

The randomized responses were thereafter given to a panel of eight prostate cancer specialists, specifically medical professionals. These doctors are affiliated with the leading hospital in Bucharest, Romania, renowned for its treatment of the highest number of prostate cancer patients each year. We selected this hospital specifically to guarantee our

access to the most distinguished Romanian medical professionals in this particular medical discipline inside Romania. We dispatched invitations to all the medical practitioners specializing in the treatment of prostate cancer who are associated with this particular institution in question. Ultimately, we obtained a convenience sample consisting of eight experts. All the experts are males and have an average age of 38.25 years with a standard deviation of 7.13 and a range of 20. Additionally, they have an average number of 16.88 patients per month with a standard deviation of 25.84 and a range of 79. It is observed that specialists have a relatively small to moderate range of ages, with a coefficient of variation of 18.63%. However, there is a significant fluctuation in the number of cancer patients treated every month (Coefficient of variation: 153.11%), indicating a distribution that is extremely skewed.

2.3 Variables and Procedure

We devised a data-collecting form that included the replies obtained from each information source (the three LLMs and the Romanian official Patient's Guide) for each of the 25 relevant questions on prostate cancer. Essentially, there were a total of 100 replies. We requested that each of the eight medical practitioners evaluate these 100 replies based on four criteria: correctness, timeliness, comprehensiveness, and friendliness. Essentially, each expert assigned a numerical rating ranging from 1 to 5 to each response. Specifically, each of the 100 replies was evaluated based on four criteria: correctness, timeliness, comprehensiveness, and user-friendliness.

In order to preserve the integrity of the evaluation process, the experts were deliberately kept unaware of the source of each response. In addition, we have developed this approach so as to mitigate the disparities and potential biases that may result from the differences in age and patient volume among medical practitioners in the field of cancer treatment. Nevertheless, it is crucial to consider the findings with caution due to the homogeneity of the sample in terms of sex assigned at birth, as all panel members are male medical practitioners. Given the limited and growing literature on this topic, there are currently no existing studies that examine the impact of assigned sex at birth on the distribution of responses. However, it is probable that there might be biases in the responses about this socio-demographic component, particularly sex that is given at birth.

Each panel member was given a digital copy of the questionnaire. Following that, we combined all the replies into a data frame and performed statistical analysis using the R packages available in RStudio. The data and code are freely available for replication and secondary analysis [18]. All participants willingly accepted to take part in the study after receiving a consent form. This document contains details on the research's goals and related contexts. Additionally, it stresses that the identity of the participants will be kept anonymous, and their participation will be handled with the highest level of confidentiality. Moreover, it underscores that participating in the research is completely optional. The research participants did not receive any incentives, either in the form of money or non-monetary rewards. Nevertheless, we promise to provide them with access to the data frame and all scientific outputs, including research reports, scientific publications, oral presentations, and other materials derived from the collected data.

The methods used were conducted in accordance with the applicable national and international standards and laws. All subjects provided informed consent. The privacy rights of the study participants were respected.

The evaluation procedure was carried out entirely in Romanian, allowing for a seamless comprehension among the native expert panel and enabling an examination of the LLMs' proficiency in handling and reflecting local and cultural subtleties in their replies. This strategy will guide the future advancement of ethical, diverse, equitable, and inclusive human-LLM collaboration models to enhance knowledge and understanding of prostate cancer.

2.4 Statistical analysis

We employed a variety of statistical techniques that we thought were suitable for achieving the objectives of our study. Our focus was to determine the extent of variation in ratings based on the evaluation criteria, as well as the extent of heterogeneity among experts in their assessments.

We computed the mean rating scores for each information tool while accounting for each of the four assessment criteria (accuracy, timeliness, comprehensiveness, and being

friendly). The corresponding descriptive statistics are useful for detecting variation in the assessment scores. Then, we performed an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to examine the differences in scores provided by the experts across the information tools (ChatGPT, the Guide, Co-Pilot, and Gemini) and the four criteria of assessment (accuracy, timeliness, comprehensive, and friendly). We deployed ANOVA for several reasons. First, we have multiple groups (tools and criteria), and we wanted to determine if there are statistically significant differences in scores across these groups. Second, by including an interaction term (tools and criteria), we sought to identify not only the main effects (tools and criteria) but also the interaction effects between these factors. In our ANOVA model, the dependent variable was represented by the expert scores. Also, our main effects were represented by the differences in mean scores across tools (*tool* effect) and across criteria (*criterion* effect). The interaction effect tests if the influence of a tool depends on the criterion used. An ANOVA model was set to indicate if both tools and criteria have significant effects on the experts' scores. And if the performance of a tool varies depending on the criterion. Moreover, we used a Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) to examine the effect of tools on multiple evaluation criteria simultaneously. In our MANOVA model, we used the scores across the four evaluation criteria as the dependent variable and the information tools as the independent variable. We were interested in gauging how much variation in the evaluation was due to the difference between tools.

We assessed the reliability and agreement of ratings among the eight experts using Intraclass Correlation Coefficients (ICC). We wanted to determine whether the experts were consistent in their scoring and whether they agreed on the absolute scores assigned. We analyzed both the reliability of individual experts and the reliability of the average scores of all experts. Essentially, we aimed to understand the degree of agreement among experts. The ICCs were computed under assumptions of absolute agreement and consistency, considering both individual and average ratings.

Lastly, we fit a linear mixed-effects model to analyze the effects of experts, criteria, and tools on the scores. We addressed the data set as having a hierarchical structure, where scores are nested within experts, criteria, and tools. We looked at random effects (experts, criteria, and tools) to account for variability among experts and among criteria. We also examined the fixed effects to understand the impact of tools on scores. In our case, the repeated measures represented the situation where each expert provided multiple ratings across different tools and criteria (this required accounting for within-subject correlations).

In a nutshell, we consider that these statistical analyses provided robust evidence of the significant and variable impact of tools on evaluation scores across different criteria while also highlighting whether experts assessed these tools in a consistent and reliable manner when considered as a group.

3. Results

Table 1 reports how the panel experts rated each information tool across the four criteria (accuracy, comprehensiveness, timeliness, and being friendly). ChatGPT seems to have, on average, better scores than the other LLMs and the official Guide. We also showcase that the ratings associated with the Guide tend to have a higher variation (spread) in comparison to the other tools (i.e., the standard deviation, SD, is higher than 1.1).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	tool	criterion	Mean	Median	SD
1	ChatGPT	accuracy	4.13	4	0.816
2	ChatGPT	comprehensiveness	4.08	4	0.772

3	ChatGPT	timeliness	4.15	4	0.831
4	ChatGPT	friendly	4.30	4	0.796
5	Guide	accuracy	3.51	4	1.340
6	Guide	comprehensiveness	3.26	3	1.370
7	Guide	timeliness	3.86	4	1.100
8	Guide	friendly	3.83	4	1.190
9	Gemini	accuracy	3.51	4	1.010
10	Gemini	comprehensiveness	3.22	3	0.932
11	Gemini	timeliness	3.74	4	0.913
12	Gemini	friendly	3.99	4	0.924
13	Co-Pilot	accuracy	3.84	4	1.100
14	Co-Pilot	comprehensiveness	3.84	4	0.983
15	Co-Pilot	timeliness	3.98	4	0.929
16	Co-Pilot	friendly	4.22	4	0.847

Table 2. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Tool and Criterion Effects on Scores

	Df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	p-value
<i>Main effects</i>					
tool	3	179	59.54	58.73	<.000
criterion	3	107	35.73	35.24	<.000
<i>Interaction effect</i>					
tool: criterion	9	31	3.40	3.35	.0004
Residuals	3184	3228	1.01		

Table 2 reports the analysis of variance for tool and criterion effects on scores. Namely, we are comparing means across different tools (sources of information) and criteria. Basically, we examine how the choice of tools affects the scores given by panel experts, regardless of the criteria (see *tool*). Further, we look at how criterion affects scores, irrespective of the tool (see *criterion*). Aside from these main effects, we assess the interaction between *tool* and *criterion*: whether the effect of a tool on the scores changes with different criteria. For example, one tool might be better for *accuracy* but not as good for easy to use (i.e., being *friendly*). **Table 2** reveals the significant main effects of the tool on the evaluation scores ($F(3, 3184) = 58.73, p < 0.0001$) and the evaluation criterion ($F(3, 3184) = 35.24, p < 0.0001$), indicating substantial differences in scores across different tools and criteria used. Furthermore, the interaction between tool type and evaluation criterion was also significant ($F(9, 3184) = 3.35, p = 0.0004$), suggesting that the impact of each tool on evaluation scores varies depending on the specific criterion applied. In a nutshell, the

statistical analysis was conducted using a two-way ANOVA, and it demonstrated significant effects for both tool and criterion, as well as their interaction.

In the analysis of evaluation scores across multiple criteria, a multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was conducted to determine the effect of the tools on the combined dependent variables: accuracy, comprehensiveness, timeliness, and friendliness. The MANOVA results, as indicated by Pillai's trace, showed a significant multivariate effect of the tool on the set of evaluation criteria (Pillai's trace = 0.14811, $F(12, 2385) = 10.322$, $p < 0.0001$). This significant finding suggests that the differences in tools are not only statistically significant but also practically relevant across the combined criteria. These results underscore the impact that tool choice has on the evaluation outcomes, confirming that the selection of tools influences various aspects of performance assessment in a measurable and substantial way.

Table 3. Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) Results for Tool Impact on Evaluation Criteria

Source	Pillai's Trace	Approx. F-value	Df	Numerator Df	Denominator Df	P-value
Tool	0.14811	10.322	3	12	2385	<.001
Residuals			769			

Note: $p < 0.001$, indicating a statistically significant multivariate effect of tools on evaluation criteria.

In assessing the consistency of expert ratings, we computed Intraclass Correlation Coefficients (ICCs) to evaluate the reliability across different assumptions of rater effects. The reliability of individual raters was relatively low with ICC values around 0.24 to 0.29, suggesting notable variability in individual assessments ($F(99, 3069) = 14$, $p < .000$). However, when averaging across the 32 ratings (i.e., each expert assessed four criteria), the reliability markedly improved, with ICC values ranging from 0.91 to 0.93, indicating excellent consistency of averaged ratings ($F(99, 3100) = 11$, $p < .000$). (See **Table 4** for detailed ICC statistics)

Table 4. Intraclass Correlation Coefficients (ICCs) for Rater Reliability Assessment

	ICC	F	df1	df2	p
Single raters absolute	0.24	11	99	3100	<.000
Single random raters	0.24	14	99	3069	<.000
Single fixed raters	0.29	14	99	3069	<.000
Average raters absolute	0.91	11	99	3100	<.000
Average random raters	0.91	14	99	3069	<.000
Average fixed raters	0.93	14	99	3069	<.000

Table 5 displays a linear mixed-effects model that we fitted to evaluate the impact of individual experts, criteria, and tools on evaluation scores (REML criterion = 8801.3). The analysis revealed significant variability among experts ($\sigma^2 = 0.13773$), with lesser vari-

ability attributed to criteria and tools. Put differently, differences among experts account for more variability in the scores than the criterion or tool alone. The overall average score was significantly different from zero (intercept = 3.8425, SE = 0.2161, $p < 0.00001$), underscoring the influence of these factors on score outcomes (Random effects: $\sigma^2_{id} = 0.3711$, $\sigma^2_{criterion} = 0.2087$, $\sigma^2_{tool} = 0.2707$; Residual $\sigma^2 = 0.9486$). All in all, the results reported in **Table 5** suggest significant variability in scores attributed to differences among experts, with lesser but still notable variability due to criteria and tools. The overall mean score (intercept) is significantly different from zero, indicating a meaningful average effect across all groups when controlling for random variations.

Table 5. Summary of Linear Mixed-Effects Model for Scores by Experts, Criteria, and Tools

Model Fit Statistics					
Number of observations	3200				
REML Criterion	8801.3				
Random Effects	Variance	Std. Dev.			
id (Intercept)	0.13773	0.3711			
criterion (Intercept)	0.04354	0.2087			
tool (Intercept)	0.07331	0.2707			
Residual	0.89983	0.9486			
Fixed effects	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t-value	p-value
Intercept	3.8425	0.2161	10.8697	17.78	<0.00001

4. Discussion

The results of our study offer useful insights into the assessment of different LLMs by a group of experts based on various criteria. The ANOVA analysis revealed significant main effects for both tools and criteria, as well as a significant interaction between tools and criteria. This suggests that the performance of the tools varied depending on the assessment criterion. The MANOVA analysis provided additional evidence, demonstrating an important multivariate effect of the tools on the overall assessment criteria. Intraclass Correlation Coefficients (ICCs) revealed low reliability among individual experts (ICC = 0.24-0.29), suggesting that individual raters had variable scoring tendencies. However, the high ICCs for aggregated scores (ICC = 0.91-0.93) indicate that the expert panel, as a whole, provided consistent and reliable evaluations. The Linear Mixed-Effects Model provided further insights into the evaluation process. There was significant variability in baseline scores across experts (Variance = 0.13773), criteria (Variance = 0.04354), and tools (Variance = 0.07331). Despite this variability, the significant overall intercept (Estimate = 3.8425, $p < 0.00001$) indicated a consistent average scoring pattern across all experts. In summary, these results demonstrate that while individual experts varied in their scoring tendencies, the overall evaluations were consistent and reliable when considered as a group. The findings also highlight that the performance of different LLMs varies significantly across evaluation criteria, emphasizing the importance of a

multidimensional assessment approach when comparing such tools. In the context of prostate cancer, where accurate, precise, and empathetic communication is critical, LLMs have the potential to play a transformative role. [19]

Our results reveal several implications for the contemporary design of the doctor-patient relationship and the transition toward a truly personalized doctor-patient communication model: delivering the right message from the right doctor, at the right time, to the right patient. [20, 21] First, the three LLMs, as well as the Guide, may excel in specific evaluation criteria, suggesting that tool selection should be targeted based on the intended application. Second, aggregating ratings across experts provides a more reliable evaluation of language models. Third, future evaluations should consider different weighting schemes for criteria based on their relative importance in specific applications.

Therefore, the study results advocate for the personalization of doctor-patient communication, taking into consideration the specificities of the information source (the medical doctor), the message, and the medium (LLMs, including the Guide).

Experts in prostate cancer add significant value to patient communication through a collective contribution as a group. The role of these experts is to contribute to the training of LLM-based solutions and to continuously supervise the quality of the information provided by these solutions. [22 - 25] The Patient Guide can benefit from the development of LLMs and can transform itself into a dynamic, living, and interactive guide, an essential tool in the new paradigm of personalized communication. [26]

In the doctor-patient relationship [27], adapted from the linear model of communication, the interaction begins with the doctor or the patient serving as the information source, depending on who initiates the communication. The doctor may encode complex medical information into understandable language, or the patient may describe symptoms or concerns. The message is then transmitted through channels like face-to-face conversations, phone calls, or digital communication in telemedicine. Once received, the message is decoded by the listener, be it the patient interpreting medical advice or the doctor understanding the patient's symptoms. Throughout this process, potential noise, such as medical jargon, emotional distress, or environmental distractions, can interfere with the clarity and effectiveness of the communication. This model illustrates the need for clear and precise dialogue, with careful consideration of the communication medium and potential barriers, to ensure that both doctor and patient accurately exchange and understand vital health information. [28]

Our study highlights the importance of developing a human-LLMs collaboration model for accurately informing patients with prostate cancer. The crucial aspect is the initial and ongoing involvement of a group of prostate cancer experts, not just a single doctor, across the entire spectrum of the disease, from prevention to the most sophisticated treatments.

By focusing on personalizing communication in the doctor-patient relationship—ensuring the right message from the right doctor reaches the right patient at the right time—, we advocate for a model that integrates LLMs thoughtfully, considering their potential both to enhance and complicate medical communication (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Conceptualization of the personalized communication model through integration of LLMs in the Shannon-Weaver mathematical model of communication

LLMs can play a nuanced role [29] in the linear model of communication between the doctor and patient. LLMs can assist doctors by helping to encode complex oncological information into more accessible language, potentially simplifying explanations about treatment options, side effects, and prognostic outcomes. This assistance can minimize the noise created by medical jargon, making it easier for patients to understand their condition and treatment choices.

LLMs might also introduce new forms of noise or interference. [30] For instance, the potential for misinterpretation or oversimplification of medical advice through automated language processing could lead to inaccuracies in the information received by the patient. Additionally, the reliance on technology for communication could inadvertently distance the personal interaction between doctor and patient, potentially leading to a loss of vital nuances that are often conveyed through direct human contact. Moreover, the impersonal nature of automated interactions could diminish the empathetic communication that is crucial in oncology, where understanding patient fears and emotional needs is as important as discussing clinical treatment.

The accuracy of automated translations of medical content can sometimes be inconsistent, leading to potential misinterpretations or oversimplifications of critical health information. If not closely monitored, this could lead to a patient misunderstanding the severity of their condition, the expected outcomes of a treatment, or the importance of follow-up care. Therefore, while LLMs have the potential to enhance clarity and understanding in communicating complex medical information, they need careful integration to maintain the essential human connection and trust in the doctor-patient relationship, especially in sensitive areas such as prostate cancer. [31, 32]

There are some limitations that readers should account for. Future studies could include a larger and more diverse panel of experts to improve the generalizability. Also, including additional language models and criteria can offer a more comprehensive comparison. Furthermore, relational hyperevent modeling and other social network statistical frameworks can improve understanding of patient-medical doctor-patient interactions, especially in the context of Large Language Models (LLMs) for prostate cancer patients. This approach can uncover complex patterns and dynamics, enabling optimal integration of LLMs into medical practices, leading to improved patient outcomes and satisfaction. [33 - 35] Last but not least, assessing tool performance over time may inform about the adaptability and learning abilities of the different language models.

5. Conclusions

In the context of prostate cancer, where precise and empathetic communication is crucial, LLMs have the potential to play a transformative role. To maximize the potential of LLMs for educating prostate cancer patients, we advocate for a human-LLMs collaborative model where professional groups of medical experts in prostate cancer play a key role. They should be involved from the beginning and continuously in the development, training, and evaluation of LLMs. Our results suggest several implications for modernizing the doctor-patient relationship and transitioning towards a truly personalized health communication model: delivering the right message from the right doctor at the right time to the right patient.

6. Patents

Not applicable.

Supplementary Materials: The data, the questionnaire, the code and other related files are freely available for replication and secondary data analysis at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11217682>.

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